

ABOUT PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on the effective functioning of professors and teachers of higher education educational institutions with students in the educational process and pedagogical conditions of the culture of communication, offers oath recommendations were given

Keywords: pedagogical communication, culture of communication, need, interest, educational process activities Personality Development, interaction process information exchange, manners, culture of treatment spirituality of a person culture of speech expression of thought national tradition, pedagogical tact.

INTRODUCTION

In fact communication a person of activity spiritual and spiritual basis as a result appears along with emerging social needs. "Activity of individuals the need, interest, and interest arising as the basis of motivation such as socio-economic factors, in a certain sense, their target thoughts, desires surface to exit too reason will be Interpersonal relationships, communication has a significant impact on the formation of culture. Consequently, communication people between done to be increased activities inside leader Taking place, he considers the most important needs of a person to live in society and to be an individual

fulfills a computational need. That's why it's everyone importance for unparalleled" [4].

Thus, communication is the joint activities and needs of people come coming out different activities during each other with mutually to relationships is an entry process. The activity of each person in society mutually relationship and effect forms own into takes Because each how the work, first of all people get along with each other, transfer various information to each other, thought exchange such as complicated cooperation Demand is enough. So since each one of the person in society held place, of work success reputation his is directly related to the ability to communicate. Easy at first glance Such a process of interpersonal communication is actually very complex, human life learning during goes

BOOKS ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Communication psychological in terms of complicated the fact that about famous a psychologist BFPargin is like that writes:

- a) of individuals mutually effect process;
- b) individuals between information exchange process;
- c) one of the person another to the individual relationship process;
- g) one person's to others effect show process;
- d) to each other cooperation notice opportunities;
- e) of individuals each other to understand process

Communication has different forms and manifestations according to its characteristics. Communication material and spiritual forms of human practical

activity and its needs in itself reflection makes

Teacher's students with treatment manners

Teacher and student teacher and between students relationship and treatment their culture is reflected in their character, behavior and upbringing in practical life to be means A person's culture, first of all his handling, those around within noticeable in relation. From an educated, cultured teacher colleague, what and how to ask a student, to address this or that issue whether it is possible or not, attitude to issues related to family relations notice it is good whether it is necessary or not understands

Treatment in the process of the interlocutor the mood raise to him optimistic soul dedication, his own to the power confidence harvest to do too of the teacher the most important qualities is one. That's it separately to emphasize must the roof meaning treatment to culture have has been teacher ambition, conceit, indifference jealousy, gossip such as to vices patience do it can't and to him against will fight

A component of the teacher's culture of behavior is the culture of speech depends. Because speech and in it expressed word to the person effect doer powerful has psychological power. It is not only by its content, but by the speaker The level of influence and power is increased by the way of expressing the thought can be gained.

As the English dramatist B. Shaw said, there are more than 50 ways to say "Yes". There is a style, the word "No" has as many styles, but only to write this word has a style." At the heart of this thought is a very subtle question about the culture of communication, the meaning is hidden. The teacher's communication

is based on words and thoughts The expression of expression depends on the level, spiritual world, and culture of each teacher is based on The communication culture of the teacher is not only related to interpersonal relationships, perhaps that's it with together young people education, work release, work team, if we take into account that it is necessary for the life of the society, today the student and they are character study _ their to each other gracious to be to teach religious bigotry vein shooting present period for society humanization how much relevance can be understood.

In general when communication culture improvement universal has not lost its importance as a need. With the words of the famous writer B. Shaw saying: "Now we have learned to fly like a bird in the air and swim like a fish in the water received while to us one thing — like people to live by learning get not enough."

Arthur Conan Doyle of his work hero, famous eager Sherlock Holmes as noted: "Each person is an enigma that cannot be solved according to his own characteristics." [5]. People differ from each other in their behavior and character, but they are in between similarity known level preserved remains. So, of mankind external turkishnot only his freshness, but also his inner world, taste, human form, present appearance is the result of historical maturity. At the heart of this maturity is communication between people and it is no secret that there is a culture of dealing. Therefore, the teacher's communication in culture too reasonable the need realize get important is a task.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pedagogue-teacher the work activity during students with treatment

relations big place occupies This in progress student humanity collected knowledge, treatment to do experiences absorbs. Teacher while pedagogical serves as the main person in the process, because he is responsible for educating the younger generation and bring up task loaded. Teacher students teaching and bring up in the process, it teaches the criteria of universal and national traditions. Students understanding manners and ways of communicating mainly in the image of a teacher they get Teacher student for one lifetime ideal lesson example being stay no doubt.

Teacher with student between communication in order puter main from requirements one of the student behavior handling, student did it work fair fair is an assessment. Conversations in the process teacher some requirements compliance to do right will come:

- * In the course of his work, the teacher recognizes the value of each student as a person as respect to do confidence in the student;
- * to be kind and caring to the student, both to his joy and to his worries to be a partner;
- * students with each how in the situation communication in the process separately approach pedagogical tact must be kept.

Barc h a m e ' y o r y h u j j h o r s e s a n d · T a ' l i m r i g h t _ _ _ _ _ g i q o n u n t a l a b l a r i d a n Higher education students, pedagogic staff of educational institutions , professors and teachers implement. That is why the pedagogical staff are their own professional competence, honor and protection of values to do for:

- * manners to the rules strictly compliance reach student, students teacher-student of the person value protections;

- * students to think independently, to acquire knowledge, to work, to laws,

to parents, spiritual historical, cultural, national and universal to values to educate in the spirit of respect, careful treatment of the environment, instructive activities and personal samples with universal ethics rules, truth, justice, patriotism, goodness and another good to traits relatively attention decisions must

Our nation a lot century spiritual-national, values, spirituality set giver Quran Kareem, Hadith Sharif, Imam al Bukhari, Imam at - Thermal, Bahauddin embroidery, az-Zamakhshari, Najmuddin Kubro, Ahmad Yassavi, Sufi Hello, Solomon Bokirgani such as of thinkers priceless heritage, Al Khorazmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Al-Byeruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmud Kashgari, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Mirzo Ulugbek, Amir Temur, Babur, Alyshier Navoi, Kamaluddin Behzad such as of scholars the world science and to culture added priceless contributions study, that's it basically young generation the third renaissance foundation to create capable by doing bring up necessity is emphasized. President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated that young people Islamic teaching is of great importance in education based on universal values. Islam is the religion of our forefathers, it is both faith and religion for us is enlightenment.

Another noble human quality is forgiveness. This quality is broad It is found in people who have a heart and can tolerate the situation of others' enmity. People most of the time error they do and of mistakes to be forgiven neediness they feel

"Evil goodness with return" is called Quran in my car People Many negative problems in the relationship between thoughtlessness, carelessness comes from a rude word spoken with. A beautiful word of the teacher is good treatment,

kindness is the key. Teacher sweetness and politeness from the conditions one the voice tall both low too without doing, in moderation is to speak.

Sweetness and beautiful relationship never when, never where not for sale. There is only one way to achieve this, and that is to practice the sweet word without ceasing to do book reading and information listen, a lot to hear and analysis is to do. Treatment of the teacher who pointer is a mirror. Pedagogical skill science of the teacher from the goals one - perfect a person teaching and bring up is the result. The idea of a perfect science person has both national and universal essence and value, he embodies the highest spiritual and physical perfection characteristic of mankind is a noble idea that always encourages goodness. The idea of raising a perfect person It has always been a cherished dream of our people, an integral part of its spirituality came

CONCLUSION

In short, it is necessary to pay attention to these factors and functions in the ways of forming the communication process of higher education or students. Of course, interpersonal communication increases people's respect for each other.

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